

Debromination of 2-bromo-3-keto triterpenoids using *N,N*-dimethylaniline

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Abstract : Reflux of 2 α -bromo/2,2-dibromolupanone (1/1a), methyl 2 α -bromo/2,2-dibromodihydrobetulonate (2/2a) and 2/4 α -bromofriedelin (3/3a) with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (DMA) resulted in the formation of lupanone, methyl dihydrobetulonate and friedelin, respectively in very good yields. The products have been characterized by spectroscopic analysis [IR, NMR (¹H and ¹³C) and MS] and optical rotation as well as by comparison with the data reported in literature.

Keywords : Bromolupanone, methyl bromodihydrobetulonate, 2/4 α -bromofriedelin, debromination, DMA.

Introduction

In continuation of our studies on the transformation reactions of steroids and triterpenoids¹⁻⁴, we have recently studied debromination of α -bromo and α,α -dibromo derivatives of 3-ketotriterpenoids of lupane and friedelin skeleton. Although a number of methods for debromination are available in the literature such as potassium hydroxide in a high boiling solvents, *N,N*-diethylaniline⁵, tertiary amines such as triethylamine, pyridine, quinoline and other bases⁶, sodium hydride in THF followed by addition of aqueous hydrochloric acid⁷, the yield in each was less than satisfactory and moreover neither of them was attempted on triterpenoids skeleton and more precisely on 2-bromo (or 4-bromo)-3-ketotriterpenoids.

Although people have reported the use of DMA as a debrominating agent for steroidal ketone⁸, there is no such report of debromination of α -bromo ketone of a triterpenoid skeleton using DMA. We, therefore, undertook the present investigation towards debromination of mono and dibromo derivatives using *N,N*-dimethylaniline.

Results and discussion

Each of 2-bromolupanone (1)⁹, 2,2-dibromolupanone (1a)⁹, methyl 2-bromodihydrobetulonate (2)⁹, methyl 2,2-dibromodihydrobetulonate (2a)⁹, 2-bromofriedelin (3)^{13,14} and 2,2-dibromofriedelin (3a)^{13,14} was refluxed with DMA

for 6 h. After usual work-ups⁸, the residue in each case was chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted with petroleum ether-toluene (4 : 1) to furnish pure lupanone (4)^{10,11}, methyl dihydrobetulonate (5)¹² and friedelin (6)^{15,16}. These were identified by comparing their m.p.s and by co-TLC and co-IR and NMR data with those reported in the literature.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) was used during the investigations. IR spectra were recorded in nujol on Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. UV spectra were recorded in methanol on Shimadzu-UV 240 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on Varian Mat 711 (70 eV) and JMS-D 300 (70 eV) by EI/CI method. All the rotations were taken in CHCl₃ solution. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine chamber.

General procedure for debromination :

2 (or 4)-Bromo-3-keto triterpenoids (200 mg) was refluxed with distilled DMA (30 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, acidified with 6 *N* hydrochloric acid and was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water till neutral and was dried

over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed when a solid (175 mg) was obtained. The solid obtained after usual work up was chromatographed over a column of silica gel, developed with petroleum ether. Elution of the column with petroleum ether : toluene (4 : 1) furnished white solids which on crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture yielded white crystalline solids.

Compound 4 :

White crystalline solid, yield 95% (Found : C, 84.11; H, 11.82. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (426) : C, 84.52; H, 11.74%); m.p. 207–208 °C (chloroform-methanol), $[\alpha]_D + 15^\circ$; IR : 1710 cm^{-1} ; MS : m/z 426, 383 $[M-C_3H_7]^+$, 204 (base peak). It was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., co-IR, co-TLC, co-NMR) with an authentic sample of lupanone (4) (lit.^{10,11} m.p. 210 °C $[\alpha]_D + 16.2^\circ$).

Compound 5 :

White solid, yield 92% (Found : C, 79.32; H, 10.86. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$ (470) : C, 79.10; H, 10.71%); m.p.

192–193 °C (chloroform-methanol), $[\alpha]_D + 8.0^\circ$; IR : 1730 cm^{-1} (COOMe), $1708\text{ (CO)}\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It was found identical (mixed m.p., co-IR, co-TLC, co-NMR) with an authentic sample of methyl dihydrobetulonate (5) (lit.¹² m.p. 194 °C $[\alpha]_D + 8.4^\circ$).

Compound 6 :

White solid, yield 93% (Found : C, 85.21; H, 10.72. Calcd. for $C_{30}H_{50}O$ (426) : C, 85.60; H, 10.84%); m.p. 260–261 °C (chloroform-methanol), $[\alpha]_D - 26.5^\circ$; IR : 1710 cm^{-1} . It was found to be identical (mixed m.p., co-IR, co-TLC, co-NMR) with an authentic sample of friedelin (6) (lit.^{15,16} m.p. 255–261 °C $[\alpha]_D - 27.8^\circ$).

Reaction mechanism :

Though *N,N*-dimethylaniline is often used as a dehydrobrominating agent, this property is completely dormant in the case of α -bromo-3-keto triterpenoids. Here in this particular reaction, DMA acts as a reducing agent replacing bromine atom by hydrogen. The suggested mechanism of this reaction is shown in Scheme 1.

Note

Scheme 1

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